

Staff Training and Development as Determinants of Performance among Lecturers in Selected Universities in Ogun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Training and development as a strategic organizational learning experience to gain understanding, know-how, techniques, and practices that help employees perform current and future tasks more effectively. Importantly, this study opts to investigate staff training and development as determinants of performance among lecturers in six selected universities in Ogun State, Nigeria. The study adopted a cross-sectional survey design and used a multi-stage sampling technique to select the 1488 participants of this study. Two validated questionnaires were used for data collection, which was pilot tested through test-re-test. Two hypotheses were formulated and tested. Analysis of data was done using multiple regression analysis fixed at the 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that 45.9% of the total variance in the university lecturers performance is accounted for by staff training and development ($F_{(1,1486)} = 13.137$; $p = .000$), and a significant high positive relationship was observed between staff training and development and university lecturers performance ($r = .681$; $p = .000$). It is therefore concluded that staff training and development is a powerful component to enhance the performance of university lecturers in light of the aforementioned findings. To ensure improved service delivery, organizations should make every effort to ensure that staff members are well-motivated through training and development.

Keywords: *Development, Lecturers, Nigeria, Performance, Training*

INTRODUCTION

Productivity, personnel safety, customer service, employee growth and retention, extended learning outside of the classroom, and the use of new technologies are just a few of the forces that the educational sector has faced globally and that have an impact on organizational workforce (Noe & Kodwani, 2018). As a result, training is a crucial component for the success of both employees and organizations. However, prior studies on training and development have outlined some concerns that, in order to actualize typical benefits of training, the training and development should match with the type of job and the organization's primary goal (Chepkosgey et al., 2019), and training is not a privilege opportunity given to employees; rather, it is a necessity to develop personnel competency and improve their performance (Chris-Madu, 2020).

The amount and quality of work that an employee produces while performing the tasks that have been allocated to them determines their performance (Mangkunegara, 2012). Employee performance is the end outcome of a person's labor in doing his obligations, and it is dependent on time, skill, experience, sincerity, and other factors. According to Soehardi et al. (2022) indicators of employee performance include quality, quantity, responsibility, initiative, cooperation, and obedience. According to Nguyen et al. (2020), performance is a

measure of the success attained by employees in their place of employment, both in terms of quantity and quality. As it can either enhance or undermine an organization's reputation, individual performance is crucial in any organization (Rashid et al., 2020). When businesses perform well, they are said to be successful; when they perform poorly, they are said to be unsuccessful. In light of this, there are numerous ways to influence staff performance, and training and development are no exception (Nguyen et al., 2020).

Some academics also remind us that a lack of staff development is harmful to any corporation (Armstrong, 2010), and that it may lead to many employees seeking employment with other businesses that will provide them the proper attention to capacity building (Abba, 2018). Since the effectiveness of a company is largely correlated with the caliber of its human resources, every business should endeavor to raise the standard of its labor force (Habib, 2015), and one way to do this is through training and development initiatives (Al Karim, 2019). Consequently, training is not seen as a luxury but rather as a crucial tool for businesses that wish to compete in the global electronic market by providing high-quality goods and services (Stonehouse et al., 2020).

According to Tahir and Hashim (2014), training is modern education that focuses on people's current jobs, precise skills, and capacities to directly perform their professions. Development enhances attitudes, behaviors, and personal performance (Nguyen et al., 2020). Accordingly, training and development is a systematic process of preparing employees' behavior to meet organizational goals (Habib, 2015), and it is a tool of opportunities that develops job-related skills, strengthens staff intelligence quality (IQ), encourages a positive outlook, and improves communication skills for employee competence (Elona, 2020).

Armstrong (2006) views training and development as a strategic organizational learning experience to gain understanding, know-how, techniques, and practices that help employees perform current and future tasks more effectively. These logical intangibles can be converted into an organizational resource through the persons that obtain, infer, and apply such toward the achievement of the organizations' objectives. The primary goal of training and development is to advance the organization's overall objective. Sims (2002) emphasizes that training should focus on present duties while employee development prepares workers for prospective future tasks. The purpose of training is to give workers the opportunity to increase their fundamental knowledge and abilities in order to carry out their duties and advance their careers in respectable fields of work (Armstrong, 2010). For the organization to prosper, trained employees should therefore enhance their performance and talents at work (Famodun, 2020).

Recent studies have focused on the role that training and development (T&D) can play in motivating staff members to stay with an organization and maintain a productive workforce (Elona, 2020; Stone-house et al., 2020; & Al Karim, 2019). They found that training and development programs offered by firms equip employees with the knowledge and abilities needed to carry out their jobs efficiently. In addition, Ghalawat, Kiran, and Kumari (2020) state that while employee development heavily emphasizes employee growth and individual performance (Ahmad et al., 2013), training helps employees boost performance in their current jobs. It's possible that this is what led to the perception over the years that employees are the main factor in regulating the organization's finances.

Additionally, Chepkosgey et al. (2019) reinforced the idea that training and development is one of the pillars of effective human resource management since it promotes employee competency, commitment, and retention of skilled labor for competitiveness. As a result,

managers must develop and implement training programs to broaden employees' capability development, boost their performance, and ultimately acquire a competitive edge (Ghalawat, Kiran, & Kumari, 2020). As a result, replacing a skilled workforce in the workplace is a costly expense for management to bear (Chris-Madu, 2020). As a result, human resource managers should continually train and develop their staff's skills and knowledge to ensure effective performance in order to achieve organizational goals. According to Rashid et al. (2020), training programs have many advantages for both employers and employees, including enhancing worker competence, lowering employee turnover, assisting new hires in understanding the company culture, fostering better labor relations, and so forth. In general, a win-win situation results from effective training and growth. Active training and development is an investment in people with potential for immediate or long-term rewards (Chand et al., 2020).

The mode and conduct of training and development programs have been the subject of several prior studies using various conceptual frameworks, such as T&D on job satisfaction and job performance (Nguyen & Duong, 2020), operational factors, quality and quantity of work (Kuruppu et al., 2021), its benefits to employees and organizations (Jha, 2016), soft skills, training methodology, and employee performance (Ibrahim et al., 2017), and on employee outcomes and firm innovative performance. In light of the aforementioned, it is prudent to assume that the perspectives, concepts, and/or methodologies employed by earlier researchers are applicable and unquestionably related for better explaining the understanding and value of training and development programs for employees in any type of job or company of work (Kuruppu et al., 2021).

However, more research is still necessary. With critical observations, it was noted that many earlier research on training and development concentrated on financial institutions more so in rich nations; less attention was paid to other institutions, especially in developing countries. By employing higher education institutions as a case study, this study seeks to close that knowledge gap. Importantly, this study opts to investigate staff training and development as determinants of performance among lecturers in six selected universities in Ogun State, Nigeria.

Hypotheses

H01: There is no significant effect of staff training and development on university lecturers performance in selected universities in Ogun State, Nigeria.

H02: There is no significant relationship between staff training and development and university lecturers performance in selected universities in Ogun State, Nigeria.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

Research Design: This study adopted a survey research design of an ex-post-facto type. This is so, because the researcher was only interested in determining the influence of the independent variables on the dependent variables.

Population: The target population for this study was all academic staff of all the Universities (both public and private) in the south-west, Nigeria.

Sample and Sampling procedure: A multi-stage sampling procedure was used to select the states and the schools that participated in the study. Multi-stage sampling technique was chosen because it is a stage-by-stage system of sampling method. There are six States in the

South-West Nigeria. Sampling of the states was done through simple random sampling techniques of which three states were selected. From each of the states, three Universities were purposively selected (one federal, one private and one state). In all nine Universities were selected. Selection of the staff was done using 10% proportional sampling techniques in which a sample of one thousand four hundred and eighty-eight (1488) was selected. In all eight hundred and seventy-seven (877) female and six hundred and eleven (611) male participated in the study.

Research Instruments: Two major instruments were used for this study. These were used to obtain information concerning the variables of the study, which are staff training and development and performance. The respondents were asked to give their own agreement or otherwise on the impact of training and development on performance (teaching quality and research output). It is a 40 item questionnaire with likert response format of SA (5) A (4) U(3) D(2) SD(1). A highest possible score of 200 and a least possible score of 40 could be obtained by any given respondent. For the sample of this study, score above 45 indicate high impact.

Procedure for data collection: Employees were met at their duty post after due permission from the university authorities. Participants were informed on the objective of the study and were advised to be truthful in filling out the questionnaire.

Method of Data Analysis: Data collected from this study through the use of questionnaire were subjected to simple percentage method of data analysis, as well as multiple regression analysis (step-wise with significant level fixed at an alpha of .05. the simple percentage is to allow the reader to see at a glance some of the outcome of the result such as number of participants, age, etc. The multiple regression on the other hand was used because in one single analysis it can establish the composite and relative contributions of the predictor variables on the criterion variables.

RESULTS

Table 1: Summary of Regression Analysis of effect of staff training and development on university lecturers performance in selected universities in Ogun State, Nigeria

Source of variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-Ratio	P
Regression	141.976	1	141.976	13.137	.000
Residual	16059.202	1486	10.807		
Total	16281.178	1487			
R = .681; R ² = .464; R ² (Adjusted) = .459; Stand error estimate = 7.198					

The staff training and development yielded a coefficient of multiple regression (R) of 0.681 and a multiple regression square of .459. This shows that 45.9% of the total variance in the university lecturers performance in selected universities in Ogun State, Nigeria is accounted for by staff training and development. The table also indicated that the analysis of variance of the multiple regression data produced an F-ratio value significant at .004 level ($F_{(1,1486)} = 13.137$; $p = .000$). Therefore, the hypothesis that stated no significant impact of staff training and development on university lecturers performance in selected universities in Ogun State, Nigeria was rejected.

Table 2: Relationship between staff training and development and university lecturers performance in selected universities in Ogun State, Nigeria

		Training and Development	Performance
Training and Development	Pearson Correlation	1	.681**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0
	N	1488	1488
Performance	Pearson Correlation	.681**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	
	N	1488	1488
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

The results in Table 1 indicated that there is a significant relationship between staff training and development and university lecturers performance in selected universities in Ogun State, Nigeria. A significant high positive relationship was observed between staff training and development and university lecturers performance ($r = .681$). Therefore, the earlier set hypothesis was rejected.

DISCUSSION

The outcome of this study has established that about 46% of the total variance observed in the university lecturers performance in selected universities in Ogun State, Nigeria is accounted for by staff training and development. This implies that staff training and development play critical role in enhancing the performance of academic staff in terms of teaching and research. This finding is a further confirmation of the fact that training and development (T&D) can be used as a mechanism to motivate employees in reducing turnover and maintaining a skilled workforce (Elona, 2020, Stone-house et al., 2020 & Al Karim, 2019). Their studies concluded that organizations' training and developing programs gives personnel the required skills for individuals to execute their job smoothly and effectively.

Additionally, the study of Ghalawat et al (2020) lend credence to this finding as they reported that training and development aids employees to increase performance in their present existing roles. Furthermore, Chepkosgey et al. (2019) supported that training and development is one of the directories of human resource management practice that helps in realizing workers' competency, commitment and to retaining proficient manpower for competitiveness. Therefore, there is a need for managers to design and implement training programs to expand employees' capability building and increase their performance hence gain more competitive advantage, (Ghalawat, Kiran, & Kumari, 2020).

This study reported a significant relationship between staff training and development and university lecturers performance in selected universities in Ogun State, Nigeria. This finding corroborates the findings of some early researchers that found a significant relationship between training/development on job satisfaction and job Performance (Nguyen & Duong, 2020). Hence, training and development in academia is not a luxury but a necessary tool for universities and individuals to offering high services and producing quality output (students).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study demonstrated how critical it is to continuously assess employee training and development requirements in order to proactively foresee areas of concern that may result in enhancing their potentials and, as a result, promote the profitability of the organization through an increase in general productivity and performance. The study draws the conclusion that staff

training and development is a powerful component to enhance the performance of university lecturers in light of the aforementioned findings. To ensure improved service delivery, organizations should make every effort to ensure that staff members are well-motivated through training and development.

This study provides strong evidence of a connection between training and employee performance, which contributes to a deeper understanding of the connection and interaction between training and development and employee performance. In light of the study's findings, it is advised that need assessments be given top priority in organizational training and development in order to identify the actual performance gap between what employees are doing now and what they should be doing. In order to ensure that the training is effective, the university must first examine its own needs and take into account any gaps in its employees' abilities, knowledge, and attitudes.

Additionally, the organization should provide training and development that is tailored to the needs of the participants while also aligning with its strategic goals. Participants should be chosen for training based on an accurate assessment of their needs.

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